

ESFRI

**Strategic Role and
Future Directions**

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ESFRI STRATEGIC ROLE AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) was established to support a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy making on Research Infrastructures (RIs) in Europe. ESFRI success in fulfilling its mission has rested in three pillars:

STRUCTURE

ESFRI is a unique expert group, its mandate is defined by the Council of the European Union, and it acts as an informal body advising the Competitiveness Council. ESFRI has benefited from considerable flexibility to think outside the box and focus on long-term strategic planning while having a formal connection with EU governance bodies and the Member States/Associated Countries (MS/AC). As a result, ESFRI provides strategic advice on RI-related matters, whether requested or initiated independently.

ESFRI's independence allows strategic thinking, open discussion and problem solving and is the foundation for its ability to provide strategic, merit-based advice.

METHODOLOGY

ESFRI has developed robust, high-quality methodologies that have supported the EC and the MS/AC strategic planning, prioritization, optimisation and decision-making on the infrastructure ecosystem. As a testimony of its success the methodology developed by ESFRI has been used as a blueprint for the implementation of Roadmap, Landscape and Monitoring exercises at national and international level allowing further coordination and integration of the ecosystem.

ESFRI ensures its methodology succeeds by maintaining control, ownership, and strong quality management processes.

PEOPLE

ESFRI is composed of representatives from: 1) national delegations that include authorities responsible for political decision-making and funding and representatives with extensive expertise on RIs and 2) the European Commission. As such, national delegations play a dual role in contributing to ESFRI's knowledge pool with general expertise and providing a MS/AC perspective to achieve consensus-based decisions for the benefit of the entire EU infrastructure ecosystem; in addition to benefitting from ESFRI discussions by sharing a consolidated ESFRI perspective as strategic advice to their national authorities.

ESFRI delegates collectively provide high-level strategic advice and serve as a bridge between ESFRI, policy makers, and the research community.

Building on these principles, ESFRI has over the last 25 years brought together a wide range of infrastructures under one unified framework.

ESFRI stands now at a crossroads within the rapidly evolving infrastructure ecosystem of research and innovation which include research, technology, data and digital infrastructures. The EU has experienced a decline in competitiveness in recent years, leading to efforts to strengthen and upscale services provided by technology infrastructures to enable EU industries achieve the technical capacity and capability needed to compete globally. Simultaneously, research infrastructures have matured to the point where the focus must shift from expansion to consolidation of the ecosystem. In addition, digital and data infrastructures started to play significant roles in the discovery and innovation processes. The coexistence of multiple types infrastructures also calls for a comprehensive coordination framework to support strategic, high-level decision-making and ensure efficient operation of the entire ecosystem.

These rapid changes demand that ESFRI redefines its role in strategic planning and shaping the infrastructure ecosystem. By embracing a holistic ecosystem approach, ESFRI must ensure that its experience and knowledge continue to contribute to put coherence and efficiency in the infrastructure ecosystem of research and innovation and preserve its high-level strategic coordination role.

A pressing opportunity to leverage this ESFRI knowledge is the proposed overarching EU coordination framework for the RIs/TIs ecosystem in the recent European Strategy on Research and Technology Infrastructures¹. Strategic steering must be provided for the entire research and technology infrastructure ecosystem keeping in mind that all the elements in the ecosystem should have similar levels of maturity and compatible methodologies/procedures. ESFRI must take a strategic decision regarding taking responsibility in the design and implementation of this overarching governance structure to ensure coherence and long-term sustainability for EU's infrastructure ecosystem.

Following the process that started with the ESFRI's White Paper² and continued in the "Future of ESFRI" workshop in Brno, ESFRI's top priorities for the coming years must be:

1. Focus on a strategic holistic view to facilitate advice at the highest level

ESFRI must ensure that it retains the skills and the time necessary for strategic thinking and have clear links to EU and MS/AC governance bodies to relay this strategic guidance.

2. Ensure the consolidation of the infrastructure ecosystem

A more populated ecosystem calls for an effort in consolidation. This requires deep understanding, including protocols to promote optimisation of the infrastructures in the ESFRI portfolio.

3. Play a role in the governance and design of the infrastructure ecosystem.

An overarching EU coordination framework among elements with the same level of maturity must be based on proven methodologies that have shown success in the past.

4. Optimize and maximize the impact of ESFRI's activities and methodologies

ESFRI must outsource the more technical aspects of its activities in order to free up capacity for the new tasks and focus on strategic considerations while retaining control and ownership of the process and maintaining the quality standards.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-strategy-research-and-technology-infrastructures_en

² <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-white-paper>